

music as an invitation / music that brings us together

- Session Group: Session H
- Date: November 29, 2023 9:30 → 10:15
- Presenter(s) Name: **Késia Decoté Rodrigues**
- Chair: **Jill Halstead**
- Feedback 2: **Robin André Rolfhamre**
- Research Group: **RHiMuCE**
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Keywords: music performance, digital concert, collaboration, piano, participatory arts

In May 2023 I started my postdoc research 'music as an invitation: liveness in digital piano performances through participating audiences'. The proposal of my research is to create online piano concerts in collaboration with audience groups of women and girls, in order to investigate the impact of the collaborative aspect on the sense of liveness of these concerts via the internet. In August 2023 I started the recruitment of participants through open calls on social media and run the first online workshops. The participants include students of music, professional and amateur pianists, piano teachers, and non-musicians as well. In the first workshop, during the introductions, many of the participants said that what motivated them to join the project was the fact that the invitation was coming from me. This, included feelings of friendship and the desire to take this opportunity to keep in contact, or the perception of an opportunity to work together after following of some of my previous works. This weight of the personal aspect in such early stage of the project was indeed a surprise to me.

In this communication, I will present my postdoctoral research and will draw initial reflections on these first learnings about the relational essence of the music making process. For this discussion, I will take as reference Born's observation on the capacity of music to aggregate listeners into collectivities based on musical or other identifications (Born 2015: 32). Which, in other words, could mean: the capacity of music to bring people together.

References

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About Késia

Késia Decoté (Dr Késia Decoté Rodrigues) is a Brazilian pianist specialising in contemporary music and in interdisciplinary practices. Késia has been developing a diverse career performing as a soloist, improviser, and chamber musician, with concerts in Brazil, Europe and Canada.

Késia's recordings include 'Para a frente' (Nonclassical, London), which features piano and toy piano works dedicated to her, also 'Hour' - an album of piano and cello improvisations.

Késia's research focuses on explorations of new ways to offer the experience of classical piano performances to audiences.

Késia holds a PhD in Arts & Music and MA (Distinction) from Oxford Brookes University, Masters Degree and Undergraduate (Cum laude) in Piano from the federal university of Rio de Janeiro.

Dr Késia Decoté Rodrigues is a Marie Curie postdoctoral fellow at the University of Bergen developing a research project on new forms of participation of women and girls in online classical piano performances.